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High Energy Density Asymmetric Aqueous Supercapacitor Based on a 2D Manganese Carbide as a Positive Electrode

Debabrata Nandi^{1,2}

¹Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN), Palacký University Olomouc, Olomouc, Czech Republic | ²Maharashtra Institute of Technology (MIT), Mira Road, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India | ³Zernike Institute for Advanced Materials, University of Groningen, Groningen, The Netherlands | ⁴IT4Innovations, VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava, Czech Republic | ⁵Nanotechnology Centre, Centre For Energy and Environmental Technologies, VSB–Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava, Czech Republic

Correspondence: Debabrata Nandi (debabratnandi@mitmumbai.com) | Radek Zbořil (radek.zboril@upol.cz) | Aristides Bakandritsos (a.bakandritsos@upol.cz)

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ABSTRACT

Maximizing the energy density of aqueous supercapacitors based on MXenes remains a critical challenge due to narrow voltage windows, sluggish or irreversible redox reactions, particularly at extreme and positive potentials. Here, we report a previously unexplored etched manganese–aluminum carbide (EMAX) synthesized via a circular route from waste surgical masks, delivering sustainability alongside performance. EMAX features improved porosity, low work function (2 eV), and a layered architecture with rough surface, while encoding Mn⁴⁺/Mn²⁺ redox sites that underpin fast and reversible pseudocapacitance. In a three–electrode configuration, EMAX achieves superior gravimetric (975 F g^{−1}) and volumetric (1657 F cm^{−3}) capacitances. Its intrinsically low work function enables favorable electrode potential alignment (avoiding irreversible anodic oxidation) and effective operation in acidic aqueous electrolytes at extended positive potentials. Consequently, when paired with high-work-function nitrogen-doped graphene, the asymmetric device operates particularly efficiently at 1.6 V, reaching a specific energy of 125.5 Wh kg^{−1} and 213 Wh L^{−1} and at a specific power of 863 W L^{−1}, previously considered unachievable in aqueous electrolyte devices. Together, these results highlight work function engineering, coupled with sustainable carbide synthesis, fast and reversible Mn redox sites, and etching-induced nano-architecture, leading to a substantial performance advancement in aqueous asymmetric supercapacitors.

1 | Introduction

The growing demand for next-generation energy storage solutions has intensified the search for high-performance electrode materials [1–3]. Lithium-ion batteries currently dominate the energy storage landscape, yet their slow charging rates and degradation due to irreversible electrochemical reactions pose limitations. In contrast, supercapacitors offer rapid charge/discharge capability and ultralong cycle life, owing to reversible charge storage mechanisms. However, to unlock their full potential in

applications ranging from electric vehicles to portable electronics, it is essential to improve their energy density without compromising inherent advantages such as high power density, rapid charging, and long cycle life [4, 5].

Porous carbon-based electrodes, which store charge through electrochemical double-layer capacitance (EDLC), offer exceptional cycling stability but are constrained by low energy density [6]. To bridge this performance gap, considerable efforts are directed to the design of redox-active electrolytes [7] and electrode materials

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with superior energy densities, such as metal oxides [6], metal organic frameworks [8], layered double hydroxides [9], sulphides [10–12], and layered metal carbides (MXenes) [2, 13–21]. MXenes based on Ti, V, Mo, and Nb have been widely explored for energy storage because their metal centers and surface functionalities provide pseudocapacitance, aided by enhanced ion diffusion in 2D spaces, and structural stability [22–27]. Indicatively, Ti_3C_2 , one of the most studied MXenes, has demonstrated (in a 3-electrode setup) a volumetric capacitance of 900 F cm^{-3} , attributed to electron transfer between its surface and intercalated protons [28]. When engineered as a 3D interconnected porous hydrogel, it can deliver a remarkable 1500 F cm^{-3} [29].

MXenes achieve their highest capacitances mainly as negative electrodes in acidic aqueous electrolytes [30]. Under such conditions, hydrogen evolution becomes thermodynamically favorable, narrowing the operational voltage window [26, 28, 29, 31]. This limitation is critical, as energy density scales with the square of voltage: $E = 0.5 \text{ CV}^2$ [32]. Their operation at positive potentials could overcome this issue, because in acidic media oxygen evolution is suppressed, and MXenes are poor oxygen evolution electrocatalysts [33]. However, this has been challenging because MXenes are intrinsically unstable at positive (i.e., oxidative) potentials [24, 33, 34]. Moreover, their high work function (WF) of $\sim 3.5\text{--}5 \text{ eV}$ below the vacuum level limits their effective coupling with carbon-based positive electrodes, as carbons display similar WF [23]. Moreover, sometimes there is limited redox activity in both three- and two-electrode setups, displaying linear charge/discharge curves [26, 28, 31]. As a result, MXene-based devices rarely exceed 32.6 Wh L^{-1} (ref [35]), and only reach 63 Wh L^{-1} when high-mass metallic current collectors like nickel foam are used [36], as also evidenced from a recent literature overview [37]. Previous attempts for coupling with well-known low WF materials like MnO_2 did not result in values higher than 29 Wh L^{-1} [24]. A notable exception is a $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{RuO}_2$ all pseudocapacitive asymmetric cell [17] operating in aqueous $1 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (as detailed in Table S4), reaching 139 Wh L^{-1} (and 24 Wh kg^{-1}); however, this performance comes at the cost of employing ruthenium, a rare and expensive metal, as the positive electrode.

To overcome these limitations, we expanded on manganese-based chemistry, known for its rich redox activity [38, 39], and stability over a broad positive potential range [40]. We developed a previously unreported etched manganese carbide (EMAX), synthesized via pyrolysis of manganese acetate with carbon derived from waste surgical masks, a sustainable process aligned with circular economy principles (Figure 1). The surgical mask-derived carbon is utilized for the formation of the metal carbide phase, but also for the formation of an aromatic carbon phase, which can improve the conductivity. The derived EMAX phase delivers an ultrahigh capacitance, with stable redox activity under potentials, where other MXenes are typically unstable [27, 34]. Compared to its MAX-phase precursor, EMAX exhibits increased surface roughness, expanded 2D structure, and improved capacitive behavior, while retaining fast and reversible redox features of thermodynamically stable $\text{Mn}^{2+}/\text{Mn}^{4+}$ pairs. We leveraged these properties by using EMAX as the positive electrode in an asymmetric aqueous supercapacitor (ASC) operating stably at 1.6 V . Notably, EMAX exhibits a lower WF than many reported metal carbides, facilitating favorable electron transfer kinetics and stabilizing the electrode at extended positive potentials

when paired with high-WF negative electrodes, such as the nitrogen-doped graphene (GN_3) [23]. At a current density of 1 A g^{-1} , the EMAX// GN_3 ASC delivered an outstanding volumetric capacitance (600 F cm^{-3}) and energy density (213 Wh L^{-1} and 125 Wh kg^{-1}) at 863 W L^{-1} , outperforming state-of-the-art metal- and carbon-based supercapacitors [41–43] (as later discussed in detail). These results demonstrate the strong potential of EMAX for next-generation high-performance and sustainable energy storage systems.

2 | Results and Discussion

2.1 | Structural and Physicochemical Analysis

The MAX phase ($\text{M} = \text{Mn}$, $\text{A} = \text{Al}$, $\text{X} = \text{C}$) was synthesized using recycled surgical face masks as the carbon source. The masks were cut into small pieces, washed, and dried under vacuum. They were then combined with manganese acetate and aluminum powder and mixed by ball milling. The resulting powder was pyrolyzed at 1100°C under an Ar atmosphere for 8 h to produce the MAX phase. EMAX (MnC_xT_y , where T denotes OH, O, or F terminations) was prepared by selective etching of the “A” element from the MAX phase by treating MAX powder with 50% aqueous NH_4HF_2 at 90°C for 72 h under vigorous stirring (Figure 1).

Electrode performance benefits from a high surface area accessible to electrolyte ions. In the case of MXenes, the surface area increases with the surface roughness [44]. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) analysis (Figure 2) revealed that EMAX has an average roughness of 29.2 nm , nearly four times greater than MAX (7.3 nm), confirming effective surface activation through etching. For reference, Ti-based MXenes typically exhibit roughness between 7 and 35 nm [45]. Therefore, etching significantly enhanced EMAX roughness, rendering its surface characteristics similar to those of the roughest titanium carbides. Enhanced surface roughness improves wettability, increasing ion-accessibility and boosting electrochemical activity [46]. This is also supported with contact angle measurement and sedimentation test, Figure S1a–c.

Raman spectra (Figure 2g) show characteristic Mn–C vibrational modes in both materials: A_g out-of-plane modes at 141 and 726 cm^{-1} , and E_g in-plane modes at 182 , 394 , and 625 cm^{-1} . The D/G bands arise from the carbon content in the sample that is not incorporated in the MAX/EMAX phases. This is because the synthesis/pyrolysis of the MAX phase in the presence of the surgical masks as the carbon source leads to the formation of aromatic carbon, as evidenced from the high sp^2 carbon content in both MAX and EMAX C 1s XPS results (Figure 3b). A distinct 2D band at 2670 cm^{-1} appears only in EMAX, confirming layered structure formation [47]. Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) analysis (Figure 2h,i; Figure S1d) shows that etching increased specific surface area from 6 to $36 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and pore volume from 0.02 to $0.17 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ —values exceeding those reported for Ti_3C_2 [48]. The induced porous structure was also studied by small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS, Figure S1e). The SAXS intensity of the MAX phase shows a power-law $Aq^{-\alpha}$ decay trend, where A is a constant proportional to the specific area and α is the Porod exponent related to the scattering object fractal dimension. For MAX $\alpha = 4$,

FIGURE 1 | (a) Schematic of EMAX (MnC_x) synthesis via etching of MAX phase with NH₄HF₂ at 90°C for 72 h.

indicative of a well-defined, sharp interface of the MAX particles. Upon etching, the scattering intensity significantly increased due to the formation of pores between the exfoliated particles and the subsequent increase in the specific area of the EMAX. The pore distribution is broad (i.e., of hierarchical nature), spanning from a few nm in the interlayer spaces to tens of nanometers (interparticle spaces), and is not observable by SAXS. The Porod exponent for the EMAX decreases to 3.6, suggesting that the pore interface is still well-defined, although with some pore surface roughness introduced by the etching procedure. These surface and porosity features promote higher active site density and more efficient electrolyte interaction.

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD, Figure 2j) of MAX and EMAX show diffraction peaks at $2\theta^\circ = 26.6, 30.8, 36.7, 42.4, 43.7, 49.6, 64.3, \text{ and } 66.2$, which correspond to the (-111), (400), (311), (112), (510), (511), (800), and (422) planes. These reflections are observed in the reported Mn₅C₂ from databases (Crystallography Open Database ID-1559493 and JCPDS card No. 80-1700), but we have to consider that the present phase is etched and layered, thus with intense crystal orientation effects. SEM (Figure 2k,l) shows the morphological transformation from dense MAX particles to porous, layered EMAX, which is also confirmed by TEM (Figure S1f).

The high-resolution X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (HR-XPS) for MAX indicates the presence of Mn²⁺ (Figure 3a), while for EMAX confirms the coexistence of Mn²⁺/Mn⁴⁺. The high-resolution Mn 2p spectra of MAX and EMAX (Figure 3a) are in line with the Mn 3s spectra (Figure S1g,h). The deconvoluted C 1s spectra for MAX and EMAX (Figure 3b) show components corresponding to C=C (sp²), C-C (sp³), C-O, C=O, and COO bonds. The C=C (sp²) component extends down to quite low binding energies after etching, indicating Mn-C bonds, consistent with previous reports for MAX phase and etched materials, such as those for 3D-printed Ti₃AlC₂ [49]. Here, carbon derived from the pyrolyzed masks dominates the spec-

trum and obscures a distinct Mn-C signal. The carbon-oxygen bonds increase in EMAX and are typical surface terminations resulting from the etching process. The high-resolution F 1s spectrum of EMAX displays contributions from C-F, oxyfluoride species, and Mn-F (Figure S1i). Figure 3c shows the characteristic Al-metal signal for MAX, which disappears in the EMAX spectrum after etching. However, Al³⁺ is still detected in EMAX (Table S1, likely as intercalated species), which promotes capacitance, as reported by Lukatskaya et al. [31]. Table S1 provides the surface elemental analysis for both MAX and EMAX.

The operational voltage window (V) is a critical factor in determining energy density, since it scales with the square of the voltage. For MXenes, the window is limited by anodic oxidation on the positive side [33, 34, 50] and by hydrogen evolution at negative potentials [26, 28, 29, 31]. Although MXenes are intrinsically poor oxygen-evolution-reaction (OER) electrocatalysts [33], improving operation at the positive side, especially in acidic electrolytes, the dominant constraint at positive potentials remains surface/lattice oxidation. In ASC, a larger WF difference between the positive and negative electrode can favor a higher operating voltage [27], and also inhibit irreversible oxidation at positive potentials [51, 52]. Accordingly, strategies that modulate the WF are of high importance since they can mitigate the anodic oxidation and enable effective operation.

Ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS) measurements using He I radiation (21.22 eV) for EMAX, MAX, and GN₃ (the material selected as the negative electrode) provided the WF values, according to calculations in the Supporting Information [53]. The measured WF values are 4.04 eV for GN₃, 2.74 eV for MAX, and 2.05 eV for EMAX (Figure 4). The reduction in the WF value after etching is consistent with the strong sensitivity of MXene-like carbides to surface terminations introduced during etching (-O/-OH/-F), which are known to tune WF [54]. In this

FIGURE 2 | The atomic force micrographs and height profiles of MAX (a–c) and EMAX samples (d–f) indicate their roughness. Raman spectra of MAX and EMAX samples (g). BET analysis of N_2 gas adsorption–desorption isotherm on the surface of MAX (h) and EMAX (i) Powder XRD patterns of MAX and EMAX. (j) Scanning electron micrograph of MAX phase (k), generation of pores and layers after etching in EMAX (l).

context, this EMAX phase with such a particularly low WF (also suggesting high proclivity as an electron donor) could represent a significant breakthrough because it can facilitate better charge storage at positive potentials, higher stability, and faster redox reactions. For $Ti_3C_2T_x$, the WF values typically range from 3.4 to 4.5 eV [54], which is close to the WF of graphene-based materials (3.6–4.3 eV) [55]. Consequently, $Ti_3C_2T_x$ /graphene electrode pairs have a small WF offset, whereas the difference between EMAX and GN_3 is ~ 1.99 eV. These considerations motivate the development of an asymmetric cell based on GN_3 //EMAX, which is expected to operate effectively and stably under a wide cell voltage in aqueous acidic electrolytes with EMAX as the positive electrode.

2.2 | Electrochemical Analysis in a Three-Electrode Configuration

The electrochemical properties of the EMAX were initially evaluated using a three-electrode system in aqueous 3 M H_2SO_4 (Figure 5a). The cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves significantly deviate from a rectangular, purely capacitive profile, indicating a strong contribution of pseudocapacitive processes, particularly at lower scan rates. These pseudocapacitive processes could be attributed to the effective manganese redox transitions during electrochemical cycling, as evidenced by the co-presence of two Mn valence states (confirming thermodynamic stability) in EMAX, and by the very narrow peak-to-peak separation (ΔV)

FIGURE 3 | High resolution XPS spectra for MAX and EMAX: (a) Mn 2p, (b) C 1s, (c) Al 2p.

FIGURE 4 | UPS of MAX, EMAX, and GN₃. (a) Comparison of UPS spectra around the secondary electron cutoff (SEC) data, (b) Comparison in the valence band (VB) region. The intercept with Fermi edge data determines the valence band maximum. (c) Energy scheme for EMAX and MAX, vacuum level (E_{vac}), and WF, (d) Scheme of WF values obtained from UPS spectra showing the WF difference between positive and negative electrode.

of ca. 60 mV (Figure S4). Such a small ΔV indicates very effective, reversible, and fast redox kinetics. For comparison, MnO₂ electrodes typically exhibit ΔV in the range of ≈ 100 – 150 mV [56, 57].

At lower scan rates, the CV curves are broader and more distorted due to a dominant (77% at 1 mV s^{-1}) contribution from pseudocapacitive (diffusion-controlled) charge storage (Figure 5b). As the scan rate increases, the CV curves gradually become more rectangular (Figure 5a), indicating an increasing contribution of EDLC. A similar trend of increased EDLC is also observed in gal-

vanostatic charge/discharge (GCD) curves, which become more linear as the current densities rise from 1 to 5 A g⁻¹ (Figure 5d). The b-value calculated from the $\log(i)$ vs. $\log(v)$ relationship is ~ 0.6 , further confirming the predominant diffusion-controlled storage mechanism (Figure S2a). The specific capacitances (C_{sp}) calculated from the CV curves are 876 F g⁻¹ and 770 F g⁻¹ at scan rates of 1 and 2 mV s⁻¹, respectively (Figure 5c). At lower scan rates and current densities, where pseudocapacitance dominates, the capacitance retention is 67% up to 5 mV s⁻¹. At higher scan rates, the retention is 58% for a fivefold increase in scan rate from 200 to 1000 mV s⁻¹, with no significant change in the shape of the CV

FIGURE 5 | Electrochemical performance of EMAX in a three-electrode setup in 3 M H₂SO₄ at a mass loading of 1 mg cm⁻². (a) Cyclic voltammetry curves at different scan rates (1–20 mV s⁻¹) normalized with respect to scan rate ($i v^{-1}$). (b) Cyclic voltammetry curve at 1 mV s⁻¹ showing 77% current contribution from diffusion-controlled capacitance. (c) Rate performance at different scan rates (1–1000 mV s⁻¹) and current densities (1–50 A g⁻¹). (d) Galvanostatic charge–discharge curves at various current densities. (e) Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy data collected at the frequency range of 100 kHz to 100 mHz. The inset fits Randles' equivalent circuit in EC-Lab 10.3 software. (f) Comparison of sp. capacitance (C_{sp} and C_v) with reported metal carbides, metal ion intercalated Ti₃C₂T_x (MXene) at 1 A g⁻¹ [31], Ti₃C₂T_x and reduced graphene oxide-Ti₃C₂T_x at 1 A g⁻¹ [58], MXene h-gel: Ti₃C₂T_x hydrogel at 2 mV s⁻¹ [29], MXene clay: layered clay of Ti₃C₂T_x at 2 mV s⁻¹ [28], MXene/CB: Ti₃C₂T_x /Carbon black/Alginate at 1 A g⁻¹ [59], MXene/PVA: Ti₃C₂T_x / PVA at 2 mV s⁻¹ [60], d-MXene: d-Ti₃C₂T_x at 2 mV s⁻¹ [61], RGO-MXene: reduced graphene oxide-Ti₃C₂T_x at 2 mV s⁻¹ [35], CNT-MXene: carbon nanotube-Ti₃C₂T_x at 10 mV s⁻¹ [62], MXene/PANI: Ti₃C₂T_x/polyaniline at 10 mV s⁻¹ [23].

curves (Figure 5a; Figure S2b). The electrode exhibits excellent rate capability across a wide range of current densities as well. At a current density of 5 A g⁻¹, a high specific capacitance of 512 F g⁻¹ is achieved. Even when the current density is increased six-fold to 30 A g⁻¹, the electrode still delivers 348 F g⁻¹, corresponding to 68% capacitance retention (Figure 5c). This robust retention demonstrates the fast redox kinetics and efficient ion transport pathways within the electrode, enabling stable charge storage even under high-rate conditions.

EMAX demonstrated excellent stability, retaining 85% capacitance and 97% Coulombic efficiency after 10 000 cycles (Figure S3). Post-cycling XPS collected at the fully discharged state reveals Mn present predominantly in the Mn²⁺ oxidation state (Figure S3b,c), while the SEM images showcase the preservation of the layered structure of the EMAX phase (Figure S3d,e). Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy revealed a low equivalent series resistance ($R_s = 0.96 \Omega$), obtained from the intercept of the real axis (Z'). This indicates that the combined electrolyte resistance, the intrinsic resistance of the active materials, and the contact resistance between the current collector and active materials are minimal. The charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) was calculated to be 0.54 Ω (due to the absence of a prominent semicircle resulting in an almost vertical trajectory in the high-frequency region of the Nyquist plot), indicating minimal ohmic losses and fast redox kinetics. The magnified high-frequency

region in the inset shows a very small arc, indicating good electrical conductivity and efficient electron transport at the electrode/electrolyte interface. In the mid-frequency region, the $\sim 45^\circ$ inclination of the curve corresponds to Warburg impedance (Z_w), which reflects the frequency-dependent ion diffusion in the electrolyte. The low prominence of the 45° line indicates that diffusion limitations are minimal, and the electrode allows ions to access redox sites quickly. Here, CPE and CL represent the constant phase element and the limiting capacitance, respectively. At lower frequencies, the impedance curve becomes steep, approaching 90° , further confirming the effective capacitive behavior of the EMAX electrode [63, 64].

Overall, the improved performance of EMAX compared to MAX (Figure S4) is attributed to EMAX's larger surface area, increased pore size/ roughness, layered structure, and hence exposed electrochemically active sites. The C_{sp} reached 975 F g⁻¹ and volumetric capacitance (C_v) 1657 F cm⁻³, far exceeding the MAX phase (402 F g⁻¹, 683 F cm⁻³ at 1 A g⁻¹), as indicated by the large area under the CV and GCD curves (Figure S4a,b). C_{sp} and C_v are calculated using Equations S6–S8, and thickness is obtained using SEM [5] (Figure S5). Higher ionic strength further enhanced performance; capacitance in 3 M H₂SO₄ was 36% greater than in 1 M H₂SO₄ (512 F g⁻¹ vs. 376 F g⁻¹ at 5 A g⁻¹, Figure S4c). The GCD curves of MAX and EMAX were triangular in shape with a slight tailing of the discharge curve of EMAX (Figure S4b).

Tailing may occur due to a high concentration of ions, which reduces the diffusion rate, causing delays in charge compensation during discharging [65]. However, this effect decreases in 3 M H₂SO₄. Notably, the achieved capacitance values surpass most MXene-based electrode materials (refer to Figure 5f; Table S2) [23, 28, 29, 31, 35, 58–62, 66–69]. Other transition metal-based carbides, like molybdenum carbide [66] and vanadium carbide [69] achieved C_{sp} of 55 F g⁻¹ in 1 M LiCl and 225 F g⁻¹ in 1 M MgSO₄, even in a 1.2 V voltage window. CNT-Ti₃C₂T_x in non-aqueous electrolytes, although stable up to 1.8 V, achieved only C_{sp} of 130 F g⁻¹ and C_v of 276 F cm⁻³ at 2 mV s⁻¹ [62]. Ti₃C₂T_x clay [28] and Ti₃C₂T_x hydrogel [29] showed C_v of 900 F cm⁻³ and 1500 F cm⁻³, respectively, in H₂SO₄ electrolyte at a scan rate of 2 mV s⁻¹. Ti₃C₂T_x/polyaniline at 10 mV s⁻¹ exhibited a promising C_v of 1632 F cm⁻³ in 3 M H₂SO₄, attributed to its stability in positive potential due to intercalation of polyaniline [23].

2.3 | Asymmetric Supercapacitor Full-Cell

An asymmetric cell was assembled using EMAX as the positive electrode and GN₃ as the negative electrode in aqueous 3 M H₂SO₄. The operating voltage window of the full cell was determined by optimizing the potentials for the positive and negative electrodes (Figure S6) with a total mass loading of 2.3 mg in the mass ratio of 1:2.3 (EMAX:GN₃), respectively, according to charge-balance equation (Equation S17) [70]. The CVs for GN₃//EMAX (Figure S7a) were recorded at different operating voltages from 0 to 2.0 V at 5 mV s⁻¹ because the WF difference between GN₃ and EMAX is 1.99 eV, as earlier discussed (Figure 4c,d). The CVs suggest a very stable behavior with no increasing currents due to side reactions (hydrogen evolution reaction, HER, or oxygen evolution reaction, OER), neither at very negative nor very positive potentials, corroborating the hypothesis discussed earlier regarding the role of the WF offset. Though we selected an operating voltage of 1.6 V (Figure S7a) in order to secure stability over long cycling, since the performance was found exceptional even at 1.6 V, as discussed in the following.

The pseudocapacitive properties were also verified in the full cell, as the CV curves show broad peaks and a distorted rectangular shape, and GCD profiles showed nonlinear behavior (Figure 6a,b). In contrast, GN₃//MAX cells at 1.6 V displayed irreversible peaks and poorer stability (Figure S7b). This instability can be attributed to the narrow WF offset of 1.3 eV (Figure 4d). The GN₃//EMAX cell delivered a C_{sp} of 353 F g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ and achieved an energy density of 125.5 Wh kg⁻¹ at 0.51 kW kg⁻¹. GN₃//EMAX also showed a record volumetric energy density of 213 Wh L⁻¹ at 863 W L⁻¹. Moreover, the GN₃//EMAX cell was also evaluated after increasing the mass loading nearly five times, i.e., 13 mg (~5 mg cm⁻²; Figure S8a,b). The device showed a volumetric capacitance 514 F cm⁻³ and energy density of 183 Wh L⁻¹, at 864 W L⁻¹ power density, retaining 86% of E_v with respect to the test conducted at lower mass loading. Comparative devices (GN₃//MAX, KC//EMAX, KC is Kuraray carbon) showed significantly lower performance (Figure 6d; Table S3 and Figure S8). In addition, GN₃//EMAX demonstrated excellent cyclic stability, retaining 88% and 76% of its capacitance after 5000 and 10 000 cycles, respectively, at 20 A g⁻¹. EIS measurements before and after cycling stability tests (Figure S9b) show a slight increase in charge-transfer resistance, corroborating

the usual reduction in capacitance after cycling. The Coulombic efficiency was retained at 96% after 10 000 charge–discharge cycles (Figure 6e). A constant voltage-holding test [71, 72] was also performed to further evaluate the stability and challenge the reliability of the ASC device. Figure S9a displays the constant voltage holding test at 1.6 V for 24 h, followed by charge–discharge cycles, showing that the device retains 96% of its initial capacity after 24 h of voltage holding. The practical application of the GN₃//EMAX cell is also showcased by operating a red LED (Figure S10).

In summary, the stable and efficient operation at an extended voltage window, the large surface area due to the layered structure and roughness, and the reversible redox-active Mn active sites boost the gravimetric and volumetric performance of the GN₃//EMAX. The obtained electrochemical performance is dramatically improved compared to state-of-the-art supercapacitor cells, based on MXenes (Figure 6f; Table S4 and Figure S11) in aqueous electrolytes [17, 23–26, 40, 73, 74, 76–81], including asymmetric [17, 23–26, 74, 77] and symmetric supercapacitors (SC) [5, 75, 76]. In terms of energy content, it achieved a gravimetric energy density of 125.5 Wh kg⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹. Notably, the volumetric energy density reached a record value of 213 Wh L⁻¹ at 863 W L⁻¹ with robust stability, surpassing not only previously reported MXene-based systems but also other state-of-the-art supercapacitors (Figure 6f; Table S4 and Figure S8). For instance, Ti₃C₂T_x//polyaniline/Ti₃C₂T_x asymmetric cell delivered capacitance of 106 F g⁻¹ and 338 F cm⁻³ at current density 1 A g⁻¹ in 3 M H₂SO₄, and energy density (E_v) of 51 Wh L⁻¹ at power 1700 W L⁻¹ [23]. The Ti₃C₂T_x//RuO₂ all-pseudocapacitive asymmetric cell demonstrated in 1 M H₂SO₄, similar cyclic stability (86%) up to 20,000 cycles at 20 A g⁻¹ current density [17]. However, the E_v was 138.6 Wh L⁻¹, while the use of RuO₂ poses significant limitations in terms of cost-effectiveness, sustainability, and scalability. ASC made from similar transition metals, such as MXene-carbon fabric/MnO₂-carbon fabric, exhibited only 21 F g⁻¹ capacitance, 6.4 Wh kg⁻¹ energy density, and 84% stability after 3000 cycles [24]. These values are significantly lower compared to the GN₃//EMAX device. ASC based on MXenes, such as MXene//CDC in Li₂SO₄ electrolyte [25] and MXene//graphene [26] in PVA-H₂SO₄ electrolyte, exhibit E_v only up to ~10 Wh L⁻¹. Mn-based non-MXene hybrid materials, such as the Na/graphene aerogel/Carbon cloth//C@Mn₃O₄/CC asymmetric device [40], exhibited an energy density of 110 Wh kg⁻¹ at 27 kW kg⁻¹. Our group reported GN₃//GN₃ symmetric cell achieving 198 Wh L⁻¹ but using expensive ionic-liquids operating at 3.7 V and with substantially lower gravimetric energy density. Acerce et al. also utilized non-aqueous electrolytes with an extended voltage window of 3.5 V in a symmetric 1T MoS₂//1T MoS₂ device, achieving an energy density of 80 Wh L⁻¹, being substantially lower than that the current performance [76]. This combination for GN₃//EMAX of high gravimetric and volumetric energy density, wide stable voltage window, and long-term durability sets a new benchmark for aqueous MXene-based (and other) supercapacitors.

3 | Conclusions

This study introduces EMAX, a manganese carbide-based electrode material synthesized via a sustainable route from waste

FIGURE 6 | Electrochemical studies in asymmetric two-electrode supercapacitor cells GN₃//EMAX in 3 M H₂SO₄. (a) CV curves at various scan rates (1–20 mV s⁻¹). (b) Galvanostatic charge–discharge profiles at current densities 1 to 20 A g⁻¹. (c) Energy and power density at different current densities. (d) Comparison of capacitance and energy in asymmetric cells between the GN₃//MAX, GN₃//EMAX, and KC//EMAX at the highest obtained values. (e) Cycling stability test at 20 A g⁻¹ for 10 000 cycles. The inset shows the GCD curves at the start, mid, and end of the testing. (f) The capacitance, specific energy and stability in comparison to high-performance materials tested as electrodes in asymmetric supercapacitor full cells, TCX= Ti₃C₂T_x, Ti₃C₂T_x//RuO₂ [17], Ti₃C₂T_x//polyaniline/ Ti₃C₂T_x [23], Ti₃C₂T_x-carbon fabric// MnO₂-carbon fabric [24], Ti₃C₂T_x//CDC (carbide-derived carbon) [25], Ti₃C₂T_x// reduced graphene oxide [26], MoC_x// MnO₂:Mo_{1.33}CT₂//2D TMA⁺-MnO₂ [73], P-CNT//CNT: Black phosphorous-CNT//CNT [74], and symmetric full cells, GN₃ Sy: nitrogen-doped graphene symmetric full cell [5], MOF-C Sy: MOF-derived carbon symmetric capacitor [75], metallic 1T MoS₂ nanosheet [76].

surgical masks, which demonstrates exceptional electrochemical performance as a positive electrode in aqueous asymmetric supercapacitors. The selective etching process significantly increased surface roughness (4× compared to MAX), specific surface area (6 to 36 m² g⁻¹), and pore volume (0.02 to 0.17 cm³ g⁻¹), while expanding the layered structure and enriching electrochemically active sites. XRD indicates the transformation of MAX phase upon etching, while the precise structure requires further study. XPS analysis confirmed the coexistence of Mn²⁺/Mn⁴⁺ redox couples, which, together with the low WF = 2.05 eV, enable effective operation at extended positive potentials in acidic electrolytes. In three-electrode testing, EMAX delivered high pseudocapacitance (975 F g⁻¹, 1657 F cm⁻³ at 1 A g⁻¹), rapid redox kinetics (ΔV ≈ 60 mV), minimal diffusion resistance, and excellent cycling stability (85% capacitance retention after 10 000 cycles). When paired with GN₃ as the negative electrode with high WF, the EMAX-based asymmetric cell achieved a superior 1.6 V operating window, volumetric capacitance of 600 F cm⁻³, and record volumetric energy density of 213 Wh L⁻¹ at 863 W L⁻¹, along with 125.5 Wh kg⁻¹ gravimetric energy density at 1 A g⁻¹. The device maintained 76% capacitance after 10 000 cycles with 96% Coulombic efficiency and showed no degradation after a 24 h constant voltage hold. Comparative tests confirmed that the GN₃//MAX cell exhibited substantially lower performance, while benchmarking against previous systems revealed that GN₃//EMAX surpasses MXene-, transition-metal-, and carbon-

based supercapacitors in aqueous electrolytes in both gravimetric and volumetric metrics. Overall, the combination of high redox activity, low WF, structural roughness, and sustainable synthesis positions EMAX as a leading candidate for next-generation aqueous supercapacitors. Its performance sets a new benchmark for energy density in aqueous electrolytes, highlighting the potential of circular-economy-derived MXene-like carbides for high-performance, sustainable energy storage.

4 | Experimental Section/Methods

4.1 | MAX and EMAX Synthesis

The MAX phase (M = Mn, A = Al, X = C) was synthesized using recycled surgical face masks as the carbon source. The masks were cut into small pieces, washed, and dried under vacuum. They were then combined with manganese acetate and aluminum powder and mixed by ball milling (MILL RETSCH MM 500 NANO) in a 50 mL steel container with ten 10 mm steel balls at 30 Hz for 30 min. The resulting powder was then pyrolyzed at 1100°C under an argon atmosphere for 8 h, with a heating and cooling rate of 5°C min⁻¹, to produce the MAX phase.

EMAX (Mn_xT_y, where T denotes OH, O, or F terminations) was prepared by selective etching of the “A” element from the MAX

phase. MAX powder (< 50 μm) was treated with 50% aqueous NH_4HF_2 (weight ratio 1:10 MAX: NH_4HF_2 salt) at 90°C for 72 h under vigorous stirring (Figure 1). The suspension was repeatedly washed with deionized water and separated by centrifugation at 20 000 rpm until the pH of the supernatant reached ~ 6 . The material was then washed and rinsed with a water/ethanol mixture and isolated by vacuum filtration using a porous MF-Millipore mixed cellulose ester membrane filter (47 mm diameter, 0.025 μm pore size, Fisher Scientific, Fair Lawn, NJ, USA) and dried in a vacuum oven at 120°C for 24 h. Full Experimental details are available in the [Supporting Information](#).

Author Contributions

D.N. contributed to investigation, methodology, data curation, writing of the original draft, visualization, data analysis, and funding acquisition. S.T. was responsible for writing the original draft, visualization, and validation. A.C.P. contributed to the investigation, data analysis (XPS), visualization, and writing the original draft. G.E. contributed to the investigation, data analysis (SAXS). G.P. contributed to supervision (SAXS) and data analysis (SAXS). M.O. contributed to funding acquisition, resources, reviewing, and editing. R.Z. contributed to funding acquisition, reviewing, editing, and resources. A.B. was responsible for writing the original draft, reviewing and editing, funding acquisition, visualization, supervision, and resources.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo under the same title.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-Assisted Technologies in the Writing Process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to polish the language only. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content in depth and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File: adfm73569-sup-0001-SuppMat.docx.